

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OFWONO****FIRST NAME: ERIC EDWARDS****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4%

The author used MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

QUIZ FOR PERIOD 6

1. International academic paper writing sets out a standard for which essays must be written and precisely a format that breaks down the piece into three significant parts, and the order is?

- Introduction, Body, and Conclusion.** ¹
- Introduction, Conclusion, and Body.
- Introduction, Problem statement, and conclusion.
- Introduction, Punctuation, and precisely.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2022), 10.

2. Academic writers often consult many different sources of information about developing a proper write-up; this is okay because it allows the writers to build on using the already existing knowledge, either addressing the direction of contradictions or taking the approach of propositions. In doing this, a phenomenon described as plagiarism is quite often seen among some writers; This terminology, therefore, refers to:

Failure to cite the source of information.²

Citing the source of information.

Using multiple-approach information.

Use of secondary data.

3. Researchers answer questions related to gaps, needs, etc., which is done systematically.

Therefore, research?

Takes both the directions of exploration and exposition.³

Is only exploratory.

Only exposition.

Never exploratory.

4. Information source is categorized as...

Both: primary, secondary, and tertiary.⁴

² Ibid., 34.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago, 2018), 29.

⁴ Ibid., 37.

- Only primary.
- only secondary.
- Only tertiary.

5. The author includes a reference number as a superscript when citing In-Text, Footnote, or Endnote citations in the bibliography/reference style?

- At the end of a referenced sentence.**⁵
- At the beginning of a referenced sentence.
- In the middle.
- Anywhere.

6. In research, the term methodological congruency refers to?

- Aligning the knowledge of what is being studied, the how, and the strategies.**⁶
- The knowledge of what is being studied.
- The knowledge of how to conduct the study.
- The knowledge of the right strategies for the study.

7. Qualitative research adapts various research styles, including case studies, ethnography, phenomenology, narrative inquiry, grounded theory, action research, and critical genres. Case studies are philosophically grounded under Interpretivism/constructionism and believe reality is socially, culturally, and historically constructed. The findings of case studies are, therefore?

- Transferable and not generalizable.**⁷
- Generalizable and not transferable.
- Both transferable and generalizable.
- None of the above.

⁵ Ibid.,147.

⁶ Linda Dale. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Columbia University, 2019), 135.

⁷ Ibid., 159-160.

8. Cultural anthropology is a philosophical grounding for?

Ethnography.⁸

Case studies.

Phenomenology.

Action research.

9. Malawi has experienced a cholera epidemic for several months now. The Ministry of Health is working tirelessly to cause a situation of minimal or no more outbreaks of the same in the future. Researchers have been deployed to answer questions about why the frequent outbreaks; the challenge is that the information associated with the same is scarce; what research style should the researchers adopt?

Grounded theory.⁹

Case studies.

Phenomenology.

action research.

10. Uganda recently concluded an Ebola response in which many citizens were infected, and some lost their lives. The Health Ministry seeks to design strategies to prevent future outbreaks; what research style should the government adopt?

Action research.¹⁰

Case studies.

Phenomenology.

Grounded theory.

⁸ Ibid., 164-166.

⁹ Ibid., 171-172.

¹⁰ Ibid., 179.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Columbia University, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*. Chicago: University of Chicago, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.